

**EVALUATION AND PROPOSALS FOR THE SOUND ADAPTATION OF AN URBAN AXIS
IN THE CENTER OF THE METROPOLITAN AREA OF TUCUMÁN.**

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ABSTRACT

Given the multiple environmental problems, it is of great importance for us to raise awareness about the emission of sounds and the harmful consequences of noise pollution. Urban noise is one of the main pollutants that deteriorates the environmental quality, due to the negative effects on the hearing, physical and mental health of living beings. One of the possible strategies is through the study of the soundscape as a tool to learn and apprehend how to listen and evaluate the acoustic environment of cities. In relation to this, in the present work the study of the soundscapes of exterior spaces within an urban axis in San Miguel de Tucumán is carried out and its objective is to identify, evaluate and compare the existing sound levels to evaluate the acoustic quality and the effects caused by noise pollution, incorporating the acoustic adaptation variable to define a sustainable and healthy acoustic environment for the well-being of its inhabitants. For the research, the Participatory Action Research methodology was adopted, approached in stages. In the first, the analytical and deductive method was used. In the second, through case studies, exploratory and descriptive. The results obtained allowed to diagnose the current sound situation of these urban areas, their comparison and determination of architectural proposals for their acoustic adaptation not only within the architectural design but also urban.

KEYWORDS

Noise pollution, soundscape, urban axis, noise, acoustic quality.

INTRODUCTION

Since 1970, environmental noise has been considered one of the main pollutants. Noise pollution is the excess of sound that alters the normal conditions of the environment in a given area. It affects both the environment and the soundscape, as well as the people exposed to it, since it has important negative effects on their health and quality of life.

Sound levels, which are measured with standard instruments, define the decibels (dB) to which the inhabitants of a given space are exposed. These values constitute the unit of measurement on a scale ranging from 10 to 150 dB. The World Health Organization (WHO) states: "Unlike other environmental problems, noise pollution is on the increase and produces an increasing number of complaints from the population. It also affects future generations and has socio-cultural, aesthetic and economic repercussions" (WHO, 2004). The WHO recommends as acceptable values an outdoor noise limit of 55 dB(A) during the day and 40 dB(A) at night.

The study of the soundscape is of great importance in the management of the quality of the urban environment. This is the name given to the set of sounds in a given place or at a given time. According to Quintero and Recuero (2018), they express: "Therefore, the soundscape is simultaneously a subjective perception and a physical environment that is in constant construction and transformation, which identifies each place by its sounds, and which is studied from sound anthropology".

This article aims to study public outdoor spaces within an urban axis in the center of the city of San Miguel de Tucumán and seeks to evaluate the levels of existing noise pollution that affect the selected area. In addition, it allows us to know the differences and variations in noise pollution levels between

two different contexts: vehicular traffic streets and pedestrian streets. For this purpose, a diagnosis and characterization of the acoustic situation in 15 selected points in the urban axis is carried out, in order to identify the variables that interfere in the urban space and to interrelate the indicators that can characterize the soundscape. To this effect, sustainable technological-architectural solutions are proposed for the acoustic adaptation of these spaces, in order to achieve Acoustic Quality of the evaluated area.

In recent years, in the downtown area, the municipality has been carrying out projects for the revaluation of the Historic Center. The same, contemplates a restructuring of downtown streets, with the intention of reducing the congestion of vehicular traffic and give place to the pedestrian, with the widening of sidewalks and incorporation of urban equipment.

METHODOLOGY

The work is oriented to the study of the Acoustic Quality of outdoor urban public spaces of an important central axis of San Miguel de Tucumán. The research was developed based on a methodological combination.

In the first stage, the analytical and deductive method was used, where measurements were made with instruments according to IRAM 4113 Standard: "Acoustics. Description, measurement and evaluation of environmental noise, Part I and II". In the second stage, the case study, exploratory and descriptive methods were used, in which urban sound profiles were elaborated for their characterization, evaluation and comparison. In the third stage, the qualitative method was used, through user surveys. The data obtained were systematized and synthesized through tables and graphs, with the elaboration of a series of proposals and recommendations for their acoustic adequacy.

Urban axis analyzed

The study area includes the urban public spaces of Mendoza Street, which connects from west to east Mitre Avenue with Avellaneda Avenue. This is an important urban axis within the main roadway of the city and also on a metropolitan scale, since it structures the east-west development of the Metropolitan Area of Tucumán (AMeT). It was possible to differentiate three types of vehicles circulating along this road, according to their load:

- a) Light traffic: such as automobiles and motorcycles;
- b) Heavy traffic: vans and unloading trucks in the commercial area, urban and interurban bus lines that circulate with a significant frequency along the road.
- c) Pedestrians: people who walk along the corridor in the areas corresponding to the city's downtown area.

Once the first approaches to the sector were made, 15 strategic points were identified to characterize and learn about the acoustic conditions of the sector. Locations were chosen at intersections of the corridor under study, with different pedestrian and vehicular traffic.

Figure 1: Mendoza Street axis with the points analyzed.

Methodological tools used

In the mentioned axes and points, objective evaluations were made through instrumental measurements. For this purpose, the direct measurement of the environmental noise indicators recommended by the standards on: a) IRAM 4113 "Acoustics. Description, measurement and evaluation of environmental noise, I and II part", and b) IRAM 4062: "Noise nuisance to the neighborhood. Method of measurement and classification".

For the subjective evaluations, the socio-acoustic survey methodology was applied to users, inhabitants or passers-by of the space under study.

- **Instrumental:** Measurements were made with a Lutron Digital Sound Level Meter (Integrating Sound Level Meter SL-4035SD) class 2 with data storage in a memory card to record the values in a spreadsheet software that includes real-time recording.
The survey was carried out during daytime hours, between 16:00 hours and 19:00 hours. Each measurement lasted from 5 to 10 minutes at each selected point.
To measure human perception, type A weighting filters are used, since the human ear is unable to perceive all existing frequencies.
- **Objective indicators:** which should be considered to avoid negative effects on people.
 - a) Equivalent Continuous Sound Level (LAeq): expresses an average amount of sound energy perceived by an individual in a time interval, i.e., it represents the average noise pollution in a location, accumulated during a time interval. The usefulness of this parameter is to be able to determine the risk of hearing damage when exposed to high sound levels, being the basic and highly used measure in sound calculations.
 - b) Percentile Levels L10 and L90: which indicate the noise level that is exceeded in a certain percentage of the measurement time. The smaller the percentage of time, the higher the sound level to be exceeded. The L90 percentile defines the sound level that has been exceeded during 90% of the measurement time and is usually used for the measurement of background noise levels. In contrast, the L10 value is the level that has just been exceeded for 10% of the time and takes into account annoying noise peaks.
- **Subjective indicators:** a qualitative evaluation was carried out by means of a survey of people who live in and/or visit the area on a regular basis, involved in the perception of the noise environment, in order to know the effects of the noise in the urban channel, according to how they perceive it. These surveys made it possible to establish the reactions of the population to noise and to quantify the annoyance endured, based on the opinion of those affected, who are in direct and constant contact with the sounds of this area of the city.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the selected points, measurements were made with instruments. The data was recorded by means of:

- Survey sheets: these contained data on the activities in the area, period of measurements, building density and presence of trees.
- Sound survey: they are stored in spreadsheets in spreadsheet format that allow the generation of sound level graphs, with real-time recording.
- Urban profiles: these were carried out for each selected point and are used for their characterization. Road widths, sidewalk dimensions, façade height in front of the location, urban equipment and existing trees were taken into account.

Measurement results

Point 1 - Mendoza Street and Mitre Avenue

Commercial and residential activities can be found at the point of analysis. Vehicular traffic and public passenger transportation converge on Avenida Mitre from north to south. Therefore, the incident noise is caused by vehicular traffic.

Table 1: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 74 dBA
		L10 76 dBA
		L90 66,3 dBA

Point 2 - Mendoza Street at the corner of Suipacha Street

Area with residential activity, with greater vehicular traffic circulation along Suipacha Street.

On the other hand, a subway vehicular tunnel begins at this intersection, built to cross the urban barrier generated by the former "Central Córdoba" National Railroad Station.

Table 2: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 69 dBA
		L10 72,4 dBA
		L90 61,7 dBA

Point 3 - Mendoza Street at the corner of Marco Avellaneda Street

The Marco Avellaneda Road axis is identified as an urban corridor, directing vehicular traffic from south to north.

Table 3: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 72 dBA
		L10 76,3 dBA
		L90 61 dBA

Point 4 - Mendoza Street at the corner of José Colombres Street

In this street intersection, there are commercial and residential functions, with low vehicular and pedestrian density.

Table 4: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 70,6 dBA
		L10 73,9 dBA
		L90 62,7 dBA

Point 5 - Mendoza Street at the corner of Catamarca Street

On Catamarca Street, vehicular traffic converges with pedestrian traffic on sidewalks, of medium intensity, in the vicinity of an elementary school, a convention center and the commercial area.

Table 5: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 72,2 dBA
		L10 74 dBA
		L90 65,4 dBA

Point 6 - Mendoza Street at the corner of Salta Street

Salta Street is also an urban corridor, with vehicular traffic from north to south. Several bus lines, both urban and interurban, circulate along this road. From this intersection, Mendoza Street to the east is reduced to a section, the vehicular route changes from east to west and the sidewalks are widened.

Table 6: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 73,2 dBA
		L10 77,8 dBA
		L90 65,5 dBA

Point 7 - Mendoza Street at the corner of Junín Street

Vehicular circulation is along Junín Street, since, from this intersection, Mendoza Street becomes a pedestrian street as part of the microcenter of the city of San Miguel de Tucumán. There is a great development of commercial activities.

Table 7: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 70 dBA
		L10 73,6 dBA
		L90 61,8 dBA

Point 8 - Mendoza St. at the corner of Maipú St.

Vehicular circulation is only on Maipú Street from north to south. Mendoza Street remains pedestrian in this sector. Most of the activities are commercial.

Table 8: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 70 dBA
		L10 72,8 dBA
		L90 62,8 dBA

Point 9 - Mendoza St. corner of Muñecas St.

Crossing of pedestrian streets. Commercial activities converge in its entirety, since it is a node of great importance. Towards the northeast block there is a large educational institution (primary, secondary and tertiary level). It is the point with the lowest equivalent sound level (Leq).

Table 9: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 66,6 dBA
		L10 69,5 dBA
		L90 62,7 dBA

Point 10 - Mendoza Street at the corner of 25 de Mayo Street

Vehicular traffic is concentrated on 25 de Mayo Street. On Mendoza Street, pedestrian traffic ends at this corner and vehicular traffic starts from west to east.

The activities are still commercial, with the presence of some residential buildings.

Table 10: Sound measurement values.

Point 11 - Mendoza St. at the corner of Laprida St.

Crossing of medium intensity vehicular traffic. The activities carried out are commercial and residential.

Table 11: Sound measurement values.

Point 12 - Mendoza St. at the corner of Rivadavia St.

Vehicular traffic on both streets is of medium intensity. There is a greater presence of residential activities, with a low density of businesses and institutions.

Table 12: Sound measurement values.

Point 13 - Mendoza St. at the corner of Monteagudo St.

Area where residential activities predominate over commercial activities. Vehicle traffic is very intense along Monteagudo Street, where different urban and interurban bus lines converge.

Table 13: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 71,4 dBA
		L10 73,9 dBA
		L90 63,4 dBA

Point 14 - Mendoza St. at the corner of Balcarce St.

Transit of ambulances and private vehicles near a public health institution. The predominant activity is residential.

Table 14: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 69,3 dBA
		L10 71,7 dBA
		L90 61,2 dBA

Point 15 - Mendoza St. corner Avellaneda Ave.

High intensity of vehicular and pedestrian traffic. Residential and commercial activities.

Table 15: Sound measurement values.

Sound level graph	Urban profile	Values (dBA)
		Leq 73,3 dBA
		L10 76 dBA
		L90 66,5 dBA

Survey results

Surveys were conducted with passers-by and users of the case study under analysis. The surveys contained structured questions on annoying sounds, activities interrupted by noise, knowledge about noise pollution and the characteristics of existing urban noise.

Of the annoying sounds, 19% of the respondents mentioned vehicle horns as the main one and 15% mentioned vehicle traffic. Some activities such as studying, reading and converting are interrupted by noise.

Figure 2: User responses about disturbing sounds and interrupted activities.

55% of people are unaware of the existence of legislation on environmental noise, they consider that it is environmental noise and 80% consider that an effort should be made to reduce urban noise.

Figure 3: User responses on urban noise.

PROPOSALS FOR ACOUSTIC ADEQUACY

According to the results obtained, it is noteworthy that the values are higher than those recommended by the World Health Organization of 55 dB. For this reason, a series of proposals were developed according to areas of application, ranging from the Provincial, Municipal and Individual levels.

Reorganization of urban space

The movement of vehicular traffic has a direct incidence on the generation of noise, causing a type of pollution that affects all areas of life: work, leisure, rest, etc. Therefore, the following proposals are proposed:

- *Reduction of the number of lanes in the microcenter:*

This would be achieved by reducing, in the streets, the number of lanes to one. That is to say, as the capacity of the street is smaller, the number of vehicles traveling on it is reduced and, therefore, the noise level is lower.

- *Widening of sidewalks:*

It is oriented to prioritize the pedestrian, incorporating also, new urban furniture with sound-absorbing characteristics: benches, planters, barriers, billboards. This would achieve, new acoustic conditions in the habitat, with pleasant sensations in the users.

Use of acoustic panels

The panels will be located in the pedestrian street area: from Mendoza Street corner Junín to Mendoza Street corner 25 de Mayo. The acoustic reduction is 12 dB.

Figure 4: Location of acoustic panels.

These elements are additional to the existing pedestrian elements. They have an aesthetic function and are designed to accompany the immediate context.

Figure 5: View of acoustic panels.

Wooden acoustic panels and suspended elements are used. This solution consists of an anti-noise sunshade, with glass wool interior and perforated wood lining, stainless steel at the top and attached to turnbuckles.

Figure 6: construction details of the proposal.

CONCLUSION

In the first place, there is a great lack of knowledge among the population regarding the problem. For this reason it is necessary to become aware as an individual and citizen about social behavior habits. It is essential to generate a good awareness in society about the problems that noise can cause, generating recommendations for both individuals and the municipality about the negative effects of a noisy environment.

It has been determined that the noise levels in the different soundscapes are high and can cause discomfort and inconvenience to the daily users of this axis under study. Even the values are high in those areas where there is no vehicular traffic, so it would not be the main source of existing noise. That is to say that, in all the points, the values of sound levels are higher than those recommended by the World Health Organization of 55 dB (A).

Therefore, it is necessary to implement the proposals and recommendations of this work, in order to reduce noise pollution levels in the axis and improve the quality of life of the habitat.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.